

Significant ways to improve written communication

Isayeva Mashhura Murotaliyevna

University of Tashkent for Applied Sciences

Department of “Languages”, English teacher

isayevamashhura@gmail.com (93 948-60-88)

Annotation; It is stated that, writing skill is the significant of learning English language. Writing is a technical skill that you use to communicate effectively through the written word. Though these may vary depending on what you’re writing, there are several that transcend categories. Writing skills can more specifically include Grammar, Vocabulary, Spelling, Sentence construction, Structure, Research and accuracy, Clarity, Persuasiveness.

Key words; freelance writers, a humorous short story, employability skills

Many people underestimate the importance of having excellent writing skills. Read on to learn more about how you facilitate the improvement of what is arguably one of the most indispensable skills to have; written communication!

Believe it or not, writing, apart from the spoken word, is one of the world’s oldest forms of communication that still exists today. Think about it; while we may no longer invest time in sending letters to one another, our daily communication is always accompanied by some form of writing, be it in text messages, daily emails,

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

or posts you make on your social media accounts.

In the university space, academic writing is a whole other ball game and often takes on a very different form to other types of writing out there, but the simple fact is that you cannot achieve a high level of college writing if you don't know how to improve your basic writing skills!

In addition, Written content today connects target audiences, providing them with whatever they want or need at a click of a button. As a result, writing skills are more essential than ever.

Whether you're **writing to communicate** through email, blog post, article, social media post, white paper, or other content types, effectiveness is key.

Content creation is at the heart of marketing, and good writers are constantly in demand. To stand out, team members and freelance writers need to continually update writing skills and become comfortable with finding ways to soar above the competition. From sending emails to preparing presentations, writing is often a day-to-day task in many professions spanning diverse industries. Writing skills go beyond grammar and spelling. Accuracy, clarity, persuasiveness, and several other elements play a part in ensuring your writing is conveying the right message.

Being able to write well is a form of effective communication, which many employers see as a crucial job skill. In fact, strong communication—spanning written, verbal, non-verbal, and visual—is among the nine common employability skills that employers seek in job candidates.

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

Regardless of your role, with good writing skills, you can clearly transcribe your thoughts into meaningful messages, enabling you to share your ideas, build relationships, and strengthen your professional image.

Writing, like any other skill, is something we can get better at with time and practice. Here are some strategies for developing students own written communication:

1. Review grammar and spelling basics.

Grammar and spelling form the foundation of good writing. Writing with proper grammar and spelling communicates your professionalism and attention to detail to your reader. It also makes your writing easier to understand.

Plus, knowing when and how to use less-common punctuation, like colons, semicolons, and em-dashes, can unlock new ways to structure sentences and elevate your writing.

If you're looking to strengthen your grammar and spelling, start by consulting a writing manual. *The Elements of Style* by William Stunk and E.B. White has long been considered a staple for writers. You can find similar resources at your local library, bookstore, or online.

2. Read what you want to write.

Knowing what a finished piece of writing can look like can guide your own. If you're trying to write a humorous short story, read humorous short stories. Writing a

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

book review? Find a few and take note of how they're structured. Pay attention to what makes them good and what you want to emulate (without plagiarizing, of course). If you're working on a school assignment, you can ask your instructor for examples of successful pieces from past students.

Make reading a part of your everyday life to improve your writing. Try reading the news in the morning or picking up a book before you head to bed. If you haven't been a big reader in the past, start with topics you're interested in, or ask friends and family for recommendations. You'll gradually begin to understand what subjects, genres, and authors you enjoy.

3. Proofread.

While it's tempting to submit work as soon as you're done with it, build in some time to revisit what you've written to catch errors big and small. Here are a few proofreading tips to keep in mind:

- **Set your work aside before you edit.** Try to step away from your writing for a day or more so you can come back to it with fresh, more objective eyes. Crunched for time? Even allotting 20 minutes between writing and proofreading can allow you to approach your work with renewed energy.
- **Start with easy fixes, then progress to bigger changes.** Starting with easier changes can get you in the rhythm for proofreading, allow you to read through your work once more, and clear distractions so you can focus on bigger edits. Read through your work to catch misspellings, inconsistencies, and grammar errors. Then address the larger problems with structure or awkward transitions.

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

- **If you could say something in fewer words, do so.** Being unnecessarily wordy can cloud your message and confuse the reader. Pare down phrases that are redundant, repetitive, or obvious.
- **Read out loud.** Reading out loud can help you find awkward phrases and areas where your writing doesn't flow well.

Many computer-based tools—like spell check on your word processor, or Grammarly— can help you find and fix simple spelling and grammar errors. These tools are not perfect but can help even the most seasoned of writers avoid mistakes. Take note of any frequently highlighted words or phrases so that you can avoid the same mistakes in the future.

4. Get feedback.

Whether you're writing emails or essays, asking for feedback is a great way to see how somebody besides yourself will interpret your text. Have an idea of what you'd like your proofreader to focus on—the structure, conclusion, the persuasiveness of an argument, or otherwise.

Approach a trusted friend, family member, coworker, or instructor. If you're a student, your school might also have a writing resource center you can reach out to.

You might also consider forming a writing group or joining a writing class. Find writing courses online, at your local community college, or at independent writing workshops in your city.

5. Think about structure.

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

Grammar and spelling keep your writing consistent and legible, but structure ensures the big ideas get across to the reader.

In many cases, forming an **outline** will help solidify structure. An outline can clarify what you're hoping to convey in each section, enable you to visualize the flow of your piece, and surface parts that require more research or thought.

Structure might look different depending on what you're writing. An essay typically has an introduction, body paragraphs, and a conclusion. A fiction piece might follow the six-stage plot structure: exposition, rising action, climax, falling action, resolution, and denouement. Choose what's best for your purposes.

6. Write.

Like many skills, one of the best ways to improve your writing is to practice. Here are a few ways you can get started:

- Start a journal or a blog.
- Join a class or writing workshop.
- Practice free writing.
- Write letters to friends or family.
- Put together an opinion piece for your local newspaper or publication you like.

7. Know some common fixes.

Even if a text is grammatically correct, you may be able to make it more dynamic and interesting with some polish. Here are some common ways you can sharpen your writing:

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

<http://www.unc.edu/dept>, last visited 10 April 2010.

4. Kelly, Joe, The Importance of Writing: Past Present and Future, The RSCC Online Writing Lab, 1999.

Bibliography

1. Bloomfield, Louis, The Importance of Writing, Philadelphia Inquirer, 2004.

2. Byrne, D., Teaching Writing Skills, Longman, UK , 1988.

3. College Writing,

<http://www.unc.edu/dept>, last visited 10 April 2010.

4. Kelly, Joe, The Importance of Writing: Past Present and Future, The RSCC Online Writing Lab, 1999.

Kondrat, Alla, Importance of Good Writing, from

http://www.suite101.com/reference/good_writing, last visited 17 April 2010.

6. Importance of Writing Well. Miamian Magazine. Miami University Alumni Association, 2007

7. Paige Johnson Tan, The Importance of Writing Well: A Justification and How-to Guide,

<http://people.uncw.edu/tanp/writingwell.html>., last visited 16 April 2010.

8. Business Writing Seminars, www.linguarama.com/brochure/pdfbrochures

9. The National Commission on Writing, press release, 2003, from

http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.html, last visited 9 April 2010.

10. www.flo-joe.co.uk/cae/students/writing, last visited 15 April 2010.

11. Saxton, Brian, The Importance of Writing, AptosJunior High School, 2007.
12. Birsen Tan Tütünis, Content Based Academic Writing, tutunis@superonline.com, last visited 21 March 2010.
- Writing Skills Necessary for Employment, Says Big Business, http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.htm
- Kondrat, Alla, Importance of Good Writing, from http://www.suite101.com/reference/good_writing, last visited 17 April 2010.
6. Importance of Writing Well. Miamian Magazine. Miami University Alumni Association, 2007
7. Paige Johnson Tan, The Importance of Writing Well: A Justification and How-to Guide, <http://people.uncw.edu/tanp/writingwell.html>., last visited 16 April 2010.
8. Business Writing Seminars, www.linguarama.com/brochure/pdfbrochures
9. The National Commission on Writing, press release, 2003, from http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.html, last visited 9 April2010.
10. www.flo-joe.co.uk/cae/students/writing, last visited 15 April 2010.
11. Saxton, Brian, The Importance of Writing, AptosJunior High School, 2007.
12. Birsen Tan Tütünis, Content Based Academic Writing, tutunis@superonline.com, last visited 21 March 2010.
- Writing Skills Necessary for Employment, Says Big Business, http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.htm

THE PROGRESS OF SCIENCE JOURNAL

1. Kondrat, Alla, Importance of Good Writing, from http://www.suite101.com/reference/good_writing, last visited 17 April 2010.
2. Importance of Writing Well. Miamian Magazine. Miami University Alumni Association, 2007
3. Paige Johnson Tan, The Importance of Writing Well: A Justification and How-to Guide, <http://people.uncw.edu/tanp/writingwell.html>, last visited 16 April 2010.
4. Business Writing Seminars, www.linguarama.com/brochure/pdfbrochures
5. The National Commission on Writing, press release, 2003, from http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.html, last visited 9 April 2010.
6. www.flo-joe.co.uk/cae/students/writing, last visited 15 April 2010.
7. Saxton, Brian, The Importance of Writing, Aptos Junior High School, 2007.
8. Birsen Tan Tütünis, Content Based Academic Writing, tutunis@superonline.com, last visited 21 March 2010.
9. Writing Skills Necessary for Employment, Says Big Business, http://www.writingcommission.org/pr/writing_for_employ.html, last visited 16 April 2010.
10. White, R. and Arndt, V., Process Writing, Longman UK, 1991.